

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report describes the internal balancing of remaining sub-grid scale parameterizations, with the use of data-assimilation methods to optimize the accuracy and cost-efficiency of SR-ESMs.

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WP5

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Executive summary

The high resolution storm-resolving Earth system models (SR-ESMs) are by design solving such physical processes explicitly that have traditionally been parametrised leading to potentially substantial changes in the balance between the remaining parametrisations. This deliverable describes a cost efficient algorithmic tuning method that can be applied to regain the internal balance between the remaining parametrisations of the NextGEMS SR-ESMs. The proof-of-concept work was carried out using numerical weather prediction model OpenIFS with reduced resolution of about 50 km. The results show that successful tuning of the parameters can be achieved with a moderate total simulated time equaling about 10 years of continuous simulation. Algorithmic tuning is shown to increase of forecast skill and substantially reduce certain model biases. However, the results also show that algorithmic tuning can have unexpected impact on ensemble spread. Tuning leads consistently to improved deterministic and ensemble mean forecasts, but the impact on ensemble spread appears to be unconstrained. Ensemble spread can either increase or decrease. This is either positive or negative effect depending on the dispersion of the ensemble forecasts prior to tuning. Besides tuning, this deliverable also explores new directly observation-based model verification metrics. Filter likelihood score shows superior performance compared to some more traditional verification metrics. Filter likelihood score appears to be capable of pointing out ensemble forecasting systems that have both small error and balanced spread at the same time.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP5	Relevance in this deliverable?
To test hypotheses, and quantify processes related to aerosols, clouds and their influences on climate change with a new degree of precision and fidelity. (O1 and O2)	yes
To develop parametrisations of cloud micro-physics and mixing, and apply advanced data-assimilation methods to model tuning. (O1)	yes
To advance science and support efforts to operationalise the Paris agreement to limit global warming, through improved assessments of aerosol forcing, radiative feedbacks and climate sensitivity. (O2)	no
To exploit the online diagnostics implemented in the Development phase to investigate the impact of a changing climate on solar and wind energy production in a joint hackathon. (O3)	no

Synergies

The algorithmic tuning method and observation-based model verification yield widespread synergy between other work packages and deliverables. The algorithmic tuning and verification methods developed in the work leading to this deliverable are general. They can be flexibly applied to different parts of SR-ESMs. Therefore, synergy is seen between this deliverable and work packages 6 to 9 and with deliverables D4.1 and D4.3 of WP4. Coupling separate model components to one system may create surprising needs for tuning the remaining parametrisation schemes, to which our method would be a viable solution.

The novel observation-based model validation method filter likelihood score (FLS) has synergy with work packages 2 and 4. FLS has direct synergies with these work packages, since an observation-based model validation method is a natural choice in the case of SR-ESMs that are intended to simulate small-scale meteorological features present in real observations.

1 Tuning sub-grid scale parametrisations and assessment of internal balance of the model

Work on how to efficiently regain internal balance of the remaining sub-grid scale parametrisations in the SR-ESMs after turning obsolete schemes off has been carried out on two fronts: (1) Algorithmic optimisation of physical parameters has been explored using OpenIFS, and (2) A method for direct model-observation comparison has been demonstrated. These research avenues have produced two peer-reviewed articles Ekblom et al., 2023; Tuppi et al., 2023 and one manuscript in review Tuppi et al., 2025, NextGEMS acknowledged in all publications.

The inclusion of these three articles in this deliverable is justified with the following three facts. Firstly, the past practice of tuning of both weather and climate models has heavily relied on manual methods (e.g. Mauritsen et al., 2012). Manual tuning depends on personal skills and expertise of the model developers. This causes inefficiency in the model development and makes reproducing the results challenging. Secondly, very high spatial resolution of SR-ESMs renders parts of physical parametrisations obsolete, as the physical processes can be resolved explicitly (Rackow et al., 2025). Due to compensating effects between the parametrisations, removing one scheme can lead to distorted internal balance in the SR-ESMs, which can be fixed efficiently with algorithmic tuning. Thirdly, higher and higher model resolution mean that the models can represent features present in real observations better and better leading to need for advanced model validation methods that are based on raw meteorological observations.

1.1 Algorithmic tuning of OpenIFS model

Tuppi et al., 2023 focused on studying algorithmic balancing of subgrid-scale parametrisations. The objective was to demonstrate an efficient method for optimising model parameters of Open Integrated Forecasting System (OpenIFS) using the Ensemble Prediction and Parameter Estimation System (EPPES; Järvinen et al., 2012; Laine et al., 2012). The research question here was: Is it possible to simultaneously estimate a large [$O(20)$] number of model parameters and achieve significant prediction skill improvement. We focused on a key set of important OpenIFS model parameters and configured the EPPES algorithm to find a model parameter vector that leads to the slowest forecast error growth as measured with the moist total energy norm. The key set of parameters used here originates from an early version of the Stochastically Perturbed Parameters (SPP) scheme in IFS cy43r3 implementation (Ollinaho et al., 2017) totaling 20 parameters (19 if surface drag is considered the same for ocean and land) (see Table 3).

The algorithmic tuning was demonstrated with OpenIFS at T_L399 resolution (~ 50 -km grid spacing) with four experiments E1, E2, E3 and E_{CFM} . The initial and final parameter values are shown in Table 4. E1 is an experiment using parameter default values as starting point in tuning. E2 and E3 started with perturbed values. E_{CFM} differs from E1 so that parameter CFM is tuned separately for ocean and land areas. The final parameter values of several parameters appear to vary substantially between the experiments. However, monitoring of the tuning experiments showed that all of the experiments led to consistently lower cost function values than the respective control ensembles. Moreover, all of them led to significant improvement in prediction

skill when verified in an independent dataset (Fig. 1). Thus the recipe of Tuppi et al., 2020 turned out to be a very cost effective guide to set up algorithmic optimisation experiments. However, our method is by no means perfect yet because it also tends to degrade some aspects of the model.

The tuning exercise provided additional evidence that optimization experiments do not need to be very long and expensive. Most of the information about the optimal parameter values could be extracted with experiments consisting of $O(100)$ tuning algorithm steps using a moderate ensemble of $O(20)$ members with initial state perturbations active and forecast range of 36 hours. The main optimization experiments of Tuppi et al., 2023 used 122 algorithm steps. Combining all required weather simulations of one tuning experiment into one chunk (122 iterations x 20 ensemble members x 36 hour forecasts) equals to a total simulation time of 87840 hours, which is about 10 years. The wall-clock time of the experiment then depends on how quickly the model can run for 10 years, and how quickly the tuning algorithm can process the intermediate output. Even shorter experiments already contain useful information about the parameter values, but then the optimal parameter values may be less certain. EPPES proved to be extremely efficient in ruling out bad parameter values but fine tuning is slower.

Running several optimisation experiments revealed that the optimised parameter values can differ substantially from the default values and between the experiments (Table 4). However, verification against analysis with global RMSE revealed that all optimisation experiments led to improved performance of the model. This clearly illustrates that there is no single correct solution for the optimisation problem, but a multitude of locally optimal parameter values, each of them having a characteristic impact on model behaviour. Hence, running a number of optimisation experiments is useful in giving parameter vector proposals from which to choose the most suitable one. As EPPES always tends to converge to some optimum, output of multiple tuning experiments can be used to probe the shape of the parameter space. In our examples, a number of physically reasonable correlations between the parameters were found.

We noted the following after tuning OpenIFS with EPPES: wind components U and V at 1000 hPa improved significantly due to slowdown of wind caused by increased surface drag, and slight decrease of specific humidity Q at 250 hPa reduced the upper-tropospheric moist bias in the tropics and the subtropics. In relative terms, EPPES could decrease these biases locally by up to about 20%. A good example is shown in Fig. 2. The control model has positive westerly wind bias of $3 - 5 \text{ms}^{-1}$ in the Southern Ocean relative to operational analysis, meanwhile tuning acts to decrease this bias by up to $0.6 - 1.0 \text{ms}^{-1}$. However, even these fields contain features that cannot be fixed with algorithmic optimisation. In OpenIFS, there is a lack of low-level wind convergence near inter-tropical convergence zone that actually becomes worse in the optimised model, and the specific humidity bias at 250 hPa is not positive everywhere, but optimisation decreases specific humidity almost everywhere at that level.

An array of single-parameter sensitivity tests was also carried out in order to see what the sources of the other effects beyond the decreasing the bias of too strong wind. Most of the contribution to improvement of specific humidity, especially in the upper troposphere, comes from tuning of parameters DETRPEN, RPRCON and RAMID. At the same time these three parameters act to balance the degradation of geopotential caused by tuning CFM. Improvement of upper-tropospheric temperature can be mainly attributed to DETRPEN and RPRCON. Also,

Parametrisation scheme	Parameter name	Short explanation	Physical value
Turbulent diffusion and subgrid orography	CFM	Turbulent momentum transport to the surface	2D field (unitless)
	TOFDC	Turbulent orographic form drag	35.0 (unitless)
	HSDT	Std. deviation of subgrid-scale orography	2D field (m)
	VDEXC_LEN	Length scale for vertical mixing in stable boundary layer	2D field (m)
Convection	ENTRORG	Entrainment rate of deep organized convection	$1.75 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$
	ENTSHALP	Enhanced entrainment rate for lowest 200 hPa layer	2.0 (unitless)
	DETRPEN	Detrainment rate of penetrative convection	$0.75 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-1}$
	RPRCON	Cloud water/ice conversion to rain/snow	$1.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	CUDUDV	Convective vertical momentum transport	3D field (m s^{-2})
	RTAU	Timescale for CAPE consumption	3D field (s)
Cloud and large-scale precipitation	RAMID	Rel. humidity threshold for stratiform cloud formation	0.8 (unitless)
	RCLDIFF	Diffusion coefficient for evaporation in turbulent mixing	$3.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$
	RCLCRIT	Cloud water threshold for onset of stratiform precipitation	0.25 g/kg (ocean), 0.55 g/kg (land)
	RLCRITSNOW	Threshold for snow auto-conversion	0.03 g/kg
Radiation	ZDECORR	Vertical decorrelation distance of clouds	$0.75 + 2.149 \cos^2(\phi)$ km
	ZSIQCW	Std. deviation of horizontal distribution of cloud water	1.0 (unitless)
	ZRADEFF	Effective radius of cloud water and ice particles	3D field (m)
	ZHS_VDAERO	Scale height of aerosol normal vertical distribution	2D field (m)
	DELTA_AERO	Aerosol optical thickness	2D field (m)

Table 3: Short explanations of the parameters used in the optimisation. Parameters are categorised by parametrisation schemes (from Ollinaho et al., 2017; ECMWF, 2017).

Parameter	E1	E2	E3	E _{CFM}
CFM	(1.00), 1.14	(1.05), 1.16	(0.95), 1.19	(1.00/1.00), 1.10/0.91
TOFDC	(1.00), 0.91	(0.95), 1.14	(1.05), 0.94	(1.00), 0.87
HSDT	(1.00), 0.88	(1.05), 1.04	(0.95), 1.05	(1.00), 1.04
VDEXC_LEN	(1.00), 0.93	(0.95), 0.83	(1.05), 0.92	(1.00), 0.86
ENTRORG	(1.00), 1.00	(1.05), 1.00	(0.95), 1.02	(1.00), 1.12
ENTSHALP	(1.00), 1.05	(0.95), 0.97	(1.05), 1.21	(1.00), 1.01
DETRPEN	(1.00), 1.15	(1.05), 1.29	(0.95), 1.12	(1.00), 1.18
RPRCON	(1.00), 1.13	(0.95), 1.08	(1.05), 1.28	(1.00), 1.08
CUDUDV	(1.00), 1.01	(1.05), 1.01	(0.95), 1.01	(1.00), 1.01
RTAU	(1.00), 1.01	(0.95), 0.88	(1.05), 0.92	(1.00), 0.86
RAMID	(1.00), 0.93	(1.05), 1.03	(0.95), 0.92	(1.00), 0.80
RCLDIFF	(1.00), 1.06	(0.95), 0.85	(1.05), 1.19	(1.00), 1.01
RCLCRIT	(1.00), 1.06	(1.05), 1.04	(0.95), 0.95	(1.00), 1.20
RLCRITSNOW	(1.00), 0.92	(0.95), 1.04	(1.05), 0.92	(1.00), 1.02
ZDECORR	(1.00), 1.08	(1.05), 0.99	(0.95), 0.79	(1.00), 0.98
ZSIQCW	(1.00), 1.22	(0.95), 1.07	(1.05), 1.15	(1.00), 1.04
ZRADEFF	(1.00), 1.22	(1.05), 0.97	(0.95), 0.92	(1.00), 0.98
ZHS_VDAERO	(1.00), 0.98	(0.95), 1.19	(1.05), 0.87	(1.00), 0.82
DELTA_AERO	(1.00), 0.76	(1.05), 0.96	(0.95), 1.08	(1.00), 0.96

Table 4: Summary of parameter values in the four tuning experiments. The parameter values are expressed relative to their default values in OpenIFS. Initial parameter values are shown in brackets with gray font and final values with black font. Experiment E_{CFM} tuned parameter CFM separately for sea (first value) and land areas (second value).

Figure 1: Verification of four algorithmic tuning experiments using global Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) scorecards with respect to the default model. The x-axis of each panel shows the forecast range (h), and the y-axis shows the atmospheric variables used: Z is geopotential; U and V are the zonal and meridional components of wind, respectively; T is temperature; and Q is specific humidity. The Z, U, V, T, and Q are verified at six pressure levels from the top down: 100, 250, 500, 700, 850, and 1000 hPa. The two-dimensional variables at the bottom of the panels are 2-m temperature (t2m), mean sea level pressure (mslp), 10-m zonal and meridional wind (u10m; v10m), total cloud cover (tcc), low cloud cover (lcc), medium cloud cover (mcc), high cloud cover (hcc), and total column of water vapor (tcwv). Blue color means that the optimized model outperforms the default model in verification against operational analysis. Black dots indicate that the difference between the optimized and default models is statistically significant at the 95% level according to a two-sample t test. Geopotential data at 100 and 250 hPa are missing because of missing operational analysis.

ZSIGQCW has a weak positive effect on most of the verified variables, especially at short and long (7–10 day) forecast ranges. However, this kind of analysis obscures any potential compound effects caused by changing values of multiple parameters simultaneously, which can be the reason why DETRPEN appears to be an important parameter in the sensitivity tests, but relatively insensitive during actual tuning.

We still foresee room for further research on the topic of algorithmic model tuning with EPPES. EPPES seems to have some degeneracy issues with parameter covariances that have not surfaced before in trivial testing. Moreover, how much the tuned parameter values can be used across different resolutions deserves more attention. Ensemble forecasting-based tuning of high-resolution models is expensive so any means for saving computational resources are welcome. The initial results with low-resolution tuning are partly promising, but resolution-dependent biases could cause problems together with poorly constrained small-scale high-impact features.

1.2 Impact of algorithmic tuning of OpenIFS on ensemble forecasts

Tuppi et al., 2025 turned the focus on how does the algorithmic tuning affect ensemble forecasts. Tuppi et al., 2025 carried out a rigorous verification of ensemble forecasts against operational analysis and TEMP radiosoundings. We demonstrated that the model can be tuned so that both have approximately equal deterministic and ensemble mean forecast skill, but very different ensemble spreads. This context also enabled demonstration of selected ensemble verification metrics.

Tuppi et al., 2025 used the results of an array of six parameter tuning experiments. Three tuning experiments were carried out with ensemble initial state perturbations activated (ISP ON 1-3) and another three with initial state perturbations deactivated (ISP OFF 1-3). The main results are shown in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 shows how the impact on ensemble mean root mean squared error (RMSE) is relatively similar between the experiments. All panels are characterised by slight to moderate decrease of ensemble mean RMSE in the short lead times and slight decrease to neutral impact with longer lead times. However, there are some exceptions as well.

Corresponding figure about impact on ensemble spread (Fig. 4) provides a stark contrast. These scorecards show how the different model versions have notably different ensemble spreads. The two most extreme examples are experiments denominated as "ISP ON 1" and "ISP ON 2". Both of them lead to generally improving ensemble mean RMSE but "ISP ON 1" leads to mostly increasing spread while "ISP ON 2" leads to mostly decreasing spread. Naturally, as the impact on RMSE is similar but impact on spread is not, the spread-skill relationship is impacted too (not shown). Given that the control ensemble forecasting system is underdispersive (not shown), in "ISP ON 1" the ensembles become less underdispersive while the ensembles of "ISP ON 2" become more underdispersive.

Although the sample size here is a bit small, it nonetheless seems that the experiments run without initial state perturbations off (ISP OFF) experience less variability in the spread changes (scorecards d) to f) are quite similar) than the experiments with active initial state perturbations (IFS ON; scorecards a) to c) are quite different).

Figure 2: (a) Bias of zonal wind at 1000 hPa in the default model with respect to operational analysis and (b) difference of E1 model version to the default model. The arrows show the average wind speed and direction in the default model in the verification forecast dataset. Note that the color scale of (b) is one-fifth that of (a). In (a), the red color means too-strong westerly or too-weak easterly wind and blue means too-weak westerly or too-strong easterly wind in the default model depending on the prevailing wind direction. Biases stronger than $\pm 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ are highlighted with contours. For example, mid-latitude westerlies are too strong and tropical easterlies are too strong. In (b), the red color means that westerlies become weaker or easterlies become stronger in E1 with respect to the default model. Blue means that westerlies become stronger or easterlies become weaker in E1 with respect to the default model. For example, mid-latitude westerlies become weaker in E1 as well as tropical easterlies except for the north Indian Ocean. Areas that are, on average, more than 30 hPa below the surface are cut out.

Impact on ensemble mean root mean squared error

Figure 3: Ensemble mean RMSE scorecards for the models tuned with initial state perturbations (ISP ON) (a), (b) and (c), and for the models tuned without initial state perturbations (ISP OFF) (d), (e) and (f). The panels correspond to the meteorological variables, the numbers on the y-axis are the pressure level in hPa, the x-axis is the forecast lead time, the color scale is the relative change, and the dots indicate statistical significance at the 95% confidence interval. Negative change in RMSE (blue color) means that ensemble forecasts with the tuned model outperform ensemble forecasts with the control model.

Impact on ensemble spread

Figure 4: As in Fig. 3, but for ensemble spread expressed in terms of ensemble standard deviation. Positive (negative) change in green (purple) color indicates increased (decreased) ensemble spread relative to the control ensembles.

The effect of ensemble spread varying between the experiments is seen both in verification against operational analysis and against TEMP radiosoundings. In terms of RMSE the impact of tuning is almost identical in all six experiments, but impact on the spread-skill is very different between the experiments due to the varying spread. Therefore, the same conclusions can be drawn from verification against observations as was done from verification against operational analysis above.

However, Tuppi et al., 2025 were not able to identify the ultimate reason behind the differences of ensemble spread.

1.3 Observation-based ensemble verification with filter likelihood

On the front of developing objective observation-based verification methods (Ekblom et al., 2023), we demonstrated application of filter likelihood score (FLS) for verification of ensemble forecasts. FLS proved to be a versatile metric that can be used across various observation types to verify ensemble forecasts in observation space. This avoids the need of post-processing of observations, and makes FLS a resolution-agnostic score. Performance of FLS was compared to more traditional verification metrics: ensemble spread-error relationships with and without observation errors, and Dawid-Sebastiani score (DSS). The similarities between these four metrics are the inclusion of ensemble mean skill and spread of the ensemble in the metric. DSS and FLS also include a normalisation term in the form of a logarithm. Additionally, FLS considers the observation error, which is included in one version of the ensemble spread-error relationship. To compare the different verification metrics, we analysed OpenIFS ensemble forecast data, and compared the data against radio sounding data and satellite observations. We found out that FLS can distinguish between different ensemble systems and is consistent with the other metrics (see Fig. 5). Hence, FLS is sensitive enough to distinguish between different ensemble set-ups with small differences in initial value perturbations.

We analysed multivariate versions of FLS as well. Firstly, we focused on combined versions for different parts of the atmosphere. Secondly, we considered combined FLS where observations from three pressure levels are merged into one overall score. The results show that it is possible to form a combined score that can distinguish between the different ensemble systems (Fig. 6). This was expected from Duc and Saito, 2018. In our study, we compared different regions (Northern Hemisphere, Tropics, and Southern Hemisphere) and 10-day forecasts. The results are similar for the different regions and the FLS also works for longer forecast ranges. However, the importance of observation errors is less important for longer lead times as the magnitude of forecast errors increases more than the magnitude of observation errors.

We studied how FLS behaves when using different types of observations by forming a combined score with both radio sounding and satellite observations. The results show that when including both types of observations, FLS maintains its structure: in the beginning of the forecast, the score gets small values and values increase with forecast length (Fig. 7). The values of the score are of the same magnitude as when only including one observation type. Hence, concatenating both observation types for computation of a combined verification metric seems possible. We did not however compare different ensemble systems when analysing the satellite observations as we only had model counterparts from one ensemble system (EDA+SV). Finally, we looked

Figure 5: Comparison between different verification metrics for temperature at 500 hPa in the Northern Hemisphere. The solid lines show the mean value of the metric and the shaded area two standard deviations. The green lines show forecasts with ensemble of data assimilations (EDA) and singular vector (SV) initial conditions, orange with EDA, and purple with SV.

Figure 6: Combined FLS consisting of specific humidity at 500 and 850 hPa levels, and temperature and wind components at 200, 500 and 850 hPa levels. Panel (a) shows the results for the Northern Hemisphere, panel (b) for the Tropical Region and panel (c) for the Southern Hemisphere. The green line shows EDA+SV, the orange EDA, and the purple SV. The solid line shows the mean value and the shaded area is two standard deviations.

Figure 7: Illustration of combining FLS of only TEMP sounding data (a) and AMSU-A ch.5 data (b) to a combined score (c). Panel (a) consists of FLS computed from 200, 500 and 850 hPa temperature, and 500 and 850 hPa specific humidity. Panel (b) has FLS computed from AMSU-A ch.5 brightness temperature. Panel (c) shows the result of using both sounding and satellite observations simultaneously in computation of FLS. The ensemble forecasting system used here had EDA, SV and stochastically perturbed parametrisation tendencies active. The solid line shows the mean value over 53 ensemble forecasts and the shaded area two standard deviation error for three different areas: green for the Northern hemisphere, orange for the Tropics, and purple for the Southern Hemisphere.

at the effect of ensemble size by comparing the different verification metrics for three different ensemble sizes (5, 10, and 20 members). As the filter likelihood score is not a fair score, a reduction in ensemble size worsens the score. Deriving a fair version of FLS has not been done yet.

Lastly, Tuppi et al., 2025 also experimented using FLS for verification of ensemble forecasting systems against TEMP radiosoundings with encouraging results (Fig 8). FLS is clearly able to correctly point out the ensemble forecasting system having decreased RMSE and slightly increased spread leads to a more balanced ratio of skill and spread. Instead, traditionally used ensemble verification metric continuous ranked probability score (CRPS) seems not to differentiate between the ensemble forecasting systems clearly (not shown). CRPS scorecards largely resemble RMSE scorecards, which show little difference between the ensemble forecasting systems.

2 Conclusion

Overall, deliverable 5.2 yielded three scientific articles. Tuppi et al., 2023 and Tuppi et al., 2025 focused on demonstration of algorithmic tuning of a numerical weather prediction model in weather forecasting mode and on exploration of the aftermath of tuning. They were able to demonstrate that algorithmic tuning works remarkably well with a modest amount of resources implying that algorithmic tuning of SR-ESMs also has good prospects. In turn, Ekblom et al., 2023 focused on objective observation-based verification of NWP models in ensemble forecasting mode. Observation-based verification is an appealing method in the context of SR-ESMs, as SR-ESMs are intended to be able to represent at least a part of small scale features present

Impact on filter likelihood score

Figure 8: Scorecards of filter likelihood score computed relative to observational data of TEMP radiosoundings. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show models tuned with initial state perturbations (ISP ON) and panels (d), (e) and (f) show models tuned without initial state perturbations (ISP OFF). The sub-panels correspond to the meteorological variables, the numbers on the y-axis are the pressure level in hPa, the x-axis is the forecast lead time, the color scale is the relative change. Negative change in FLS (blue color) indicates that (1) the mean error has decreased and (2) error and spread have become more balanced.

in real observations.

Tuppi et al., 2023 demonstrated how to simultaneously estimate a large [$O(20)$] number of model parameters and achieve significant prediction skill improvement. An additional objective was to perform the tuning with as little computational resources as possible in order to show that the methodology is viable also in the context of computationally expensive SR-ESMs. The cost of one tuning experiment in Tuppi et al., 2023 equals to running the NWP model continuously for 10 years, which we consider acceptable. These tuning experiments led to notable increase in forecast skill and substantial reductions of certain model biases.

The key observation of Tuppi et al., 2025 is how algorithmic tuning can have unexpected side effects on ensemble forecasts. Improvement of deterministic and ensemble mean root mean squared error appear to be tightly related, so that improved deterministic RMSE generally implies improved ensemble mean RMSE. In the contrary, impact on ensemble spread appears to be unconstrained. The outcome of tuning can be either beneficial or detrimental to the spread-skill relationship depending on the spread-skill of the untuned control ensemble forecasting system. The ultimate mechanism how model parameters affect the ability of the ensemble forecasting system to maintain spread remains unclear as well as how to best control the ensemble spread during algorithmic tuning. However, the work of Ekblom et al., 2023 provides one candidate solution in form of an objective metric that constrains spread.

Ekblom et al., 2023 compared a new observation-based ensemble verification metric filter likelihood score (FLS) to more traditional verification metrics including spread-skill relationship and Dawid-Sebastiani score. Also Tuppi et al., 2025 used FLS in ensemble verification with encouraging results. We conclude that FLS is a potential score to be used both in verification and as a cost function in observation-based model tuning. FLS is able to distinguish between different ensemble system set-ups for both univariate and multivariate data. As with other verification metrics, FLS should be used with care alone. We recommend the score to be used along traditional verification metrics to provide an as diverse picture as possible of the ensemble system(s) analysed.

3 References

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